

**Daga Sassabe Zuwa Lauma: Takaitaccen Tsokaci Game da Tasirin Zamani a Kan
Abincin Hausawa**

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Citation: Sani, A-U. & Kaura, H. L. (2021). Daga sassabe zuwa lauma: Tsokaci game da tasirin zamani a a abincin Hausawa. In Mukhtar, I. *Et al (eds) Danyamusa Journal of Curent Research in Hausa Studies, Vol 1, No 1; Pp, 284-295. ISSN: 2814-2306.*

Abstract

Modernity has introduced a lot of inventions and new trends with regards to Hausa foods. This does not only concern the dietary habits of the Hausas but the totality of the process of food processing starting from land preparation through harvesting to cooking. The article investigates the influence of modernity on Hausa foods. The major objectives of the study are to examine the new inventions to the Hausa food processing and preparation processes as well as to ascertain the overall positive and negative impacts of such new trends. The research is based on *Food Neophobia and Variety Seeking* theory. It is hypothesized that the Hausas will accept modernization in their search for new tastes. The research learned that despite the numerous importance of modern inventions, they have many negative effects on personal health, ecosystem, as well as socioeconomic wellbeing of individuals, especially if not utilized properly. Finally, the paper suggested that there should be joint efforts by governments, resource persons, and media outlets as campaigns for educating and orienting the public extensively on proper utilization of the modern innovations, a strive which should be accompanied by well-planned programs to support the less privileged individuals harness the benefit.

Keywords: Modernity; Food; Farming; Cooking

Tsakure

Zamani ya zo da kirkire-kirkire da sauye-sauye da suka shafi abincin Bahaushu. Wannan bai takaita ga cimaka ba kawai, ya hada har da dukkannin matakan samar da abinci (tun daga gyaran gona har zuwa girbi) da kuma sarrafa shi. Takardar ta mayar da hankali ne kan bincike game da tasirin zamani a kan abincin Hausawa. Makasudin gudanar da binciken shi ne nazartar kirkire-kirkire da suka shafi samarwa da sarrafa abincin Hausawa tare kuma da nazartar alfanu da komabayan da wadannan sauye-sauye suka zo da su. An dora nazarin a kan ra'in *Food Neophobia and Variety Seeking* (Kyamar Abinci da Neman Nau'i). Binciken na da hasashen cewa Hausawa za su karfi abubuwan da zamani ya zo da su yayin da suke kokarin neman sababbin nau'ukan abinci masu gamsarwa. Binciken ya gano cewa, duk da dumbin alfanun da zamananci ya zo da su a wannan bangare, suna kunshe da matsaloli da dama da suka shafi lafiya, yanayi, zamantakewa, da kuma tattalin arziki – musamman idan ba yi amfani da su yadda ya kamata ba. Daga karshe takardar ta ba da shawarar cewa gwamnati da masana da kafafen sadarwa su hada hannu wurin wayar da kan al'umma da fadakarwa game da illolin da ke tattare da abubuwan da zamani ya kawo tare da hanyoyin cin gajiyarsu da kauce wa hadurran da ke tattare da su.

Muhimman Kalmomi: Zamani; Abinci; Noma; Girki

1.0 Gabatarwa

Kamar yadda duniya ba a wuri ɗaya take tsaye ba, ta kasance tana zagayawa, haka ma al'amuran duniya suke samun sauye-sauye. Sauye-sauye da ake samu sun shafi dukkanin ɓangarorin rayuwar al'ummun duniya. Wato kamar ɓangaren harshe da zamantakewa da gine-gine da tafiye-tafiye da sutura da abinci da sauran abubuwan da suka shafi adabi da al'ada, tamkar dai yadda S/Tudu, (1987) da Umar, (2007) da Abba, (2011) suka bayyana. Hausawa ma ba su kasance daban ba ta fuskantar waɗannan sauye-sauye. Al'adun Hausawa a yau sun bambanta da yadda suke baya. Irin wannan sauyi da aka samu kan al'adun Hausawa ya shafi abincinsu.¹

A duk lokacin da aka samu cudanya tsakanin al'ummu guda biyu, dole ne a samu tasirin al'adu da ɗabi'un wata al'umma a kan wata, ko kuma a samu wannan tasiri daga ɓangarorin guda biyu. Sani da Maikwari, (2019: 241) sun rawaito Gordon, (1978) wanda ke da ra'ayin cewa yayin da aka samu cudanya tsakanin al'ummu biyu, "al'adun al'ummu da suka kasance kalilan sukan nashe su koma cikin al'adun al'ummar da suka fi yawa a wannan yanki." Wannan ra'ayi ne na masu bin ra'in *Unidirectional Acculturation* (Ra'in Nason Al'adu).²

Tasirin al'umma a kan wata al'umma na iya kasancewa ta fuskar harshe ko sutura ko bukukuwa ko abinci da makamantansu. Kamar haka ne, cudanyar da Hausawa suka yi da bakin al'ummu kamar Turawa da Indiyawa da Larabawa da sauransu, suka samar da wasu sauye-sauye ga abincin Hausawa. Wannan ya shafi yanayin samar da abincin Hausawan da ma sababbin nau'o'in abincin da Hausawa suka kwaikwaya daga bakin al'ummu. Yana da muhimmanci a nazarci waɗannan sauye-sauye domin gano

¹ Muhimmancin abinci ga rayuwar ɗan adam ya sa masana da kwararru a fannin al'ada da kiyon lafiya yin rubuce-rubuce da dama dangane da wannan batu. Daga cikin rubuce-rubucen da aka ci karo da su masu magana game da abinci akwai: Yabo, (2006) da Gummi, (2008) da Baba, (2009) da Muhammad, (2011) da Ashkirani & Deepthi, (2012) da Kaur, (2017) da Wani & Sarode, (2018) da Mohiuddin, (2020).

² Domin samun farin bayani game da Ra'in Nason Al'adu ana iya duba ayyukan Park, (1950) da Gordon, (1978) da Mullaly, (2002) da Ngo, (2008) da Sani da Maikwari, (2019).

abubuwan da suka kasance masu alfanu tare da bin matakan magance abubuwan da ke da illa.

Babban manufar wannan bincike ita ce fofarin bitar ire-iren sauye-sauye da aka samu dangane da abincin Hausawa sakamakon tasirin zamani. Wannan kuwa bai tsaya kan nau'ukan abincin ba kadai, har ma da hanyoyin samar da su da sinadaran samar da su da kuma noma su. Kai tsaye takardar za ta mayar da hankali kan (i) nazartar sauye-sauye da aka samu ga abincin Hausawa, (ii) nazartar alfanun da ke tattare da sauye-sauye da aka samu ga abincin Hausawa, da (iii) nazartar illolin da ke tattare da sauye-sauye da aka samu ga abincin Hausawa.

1.1 Ra'in Bincike

An dora wannan bincike a kan ra'in *Food Neophobia and Variety Seeking*. Ba a ci karo da karfabbiyar fasssarar sunan ra'in ta gama-gari ba. Wannan bincike ya fassara sunan ra'in da: "Kyamar Abinci da Neman Nau'i." Wannan ra'i na da fahimtar cewa, har kullum dan adam na fafutukar neman nau'ukan abinci mafiya dadi da biyan bukata a gare shi. Sai dai yayin neman wadannan abinci, yana takatsantsan da guje wa wasu nau'ukan abinci musamman marasa dadi ko masu cutarwa. Tuorila et al., (2001) sun nuna cewa, tsofin mutane su ne suka fi taka tsantsan wurin zaɓen abinci sannan su ne suka fi kyamar sababbin nau'ukan abinci da ba su san da su ba.

Masana da dama sun yi rubuce-rubuce dangane da wannan ra'i. A cikin rubuce-rubucen nasu, sun yi fofarin binciko dalilan da ke ja hankalin dan adam zuwa amfani da nau'ukan abinci da kuma yadda yake kyamatar wasu nau'uka ko son wasu nau'uka. Daga cikin masana da suka yi rubuce-rubuce a wannan fannin akwai Birch et al., (1987) da Van Trijp & Steenkamp, (1992) da Pliner, (1994) da Pelchat & Pliner, (1995) da Koivisto and Sjoedean, (1996) da Pliner & Loewen, (1997) da Koivisto-Hursti and Sjode (1997) da Loewen & Pliner, (2000) da Tuorila et al., (2001) da Cooke et al., (2003) da Koester & Mojet, (2007).

Koester & Mojet, (2007: 100) sun goyi bayan Van Trijp & Steenkamp, (1992) cewa mutane da ke da tsantseni da saurin gundura da nau'in abinci su ne suka fi karɓar sababbin nau'ukan abinci cikin gaggwa. Mutanen da ba su wannan halayya kuwa yawanci sukan kyamaci nau'ukan abincin da ba su saba da su ba. Sun gwammaci su ci gaba da mu'amala da nau'ukan abincin da suka taso suka tarar kawai. A hasashen wannan bincike, Hausawa sun rungumi nau'ukan abinci da kayayyakin sarrafa abinci da zamani ya zo da su sakamakon son sauyin dandano da biyan bukata. A ɓangare guda kuwa, tsofaffi daga cikin Hausawa sun fi kin karɓar nau'ukan abincin da zamani ya zo da su.

1.2 Dabarun Bincike

An bi muhimman hanyoyi guda biyu domin tattara bayanai yayin gudanar da wannan bincike. Na farko shi ne lura. An gwada yin amfani da kayayyakin zamani da suka shafi abinci kamar su gas kuka da risho da firijin. An lura da bambanci da sauyi da suka samar tare da irin tasirin da suke da shi. Misali, naman miya da zai ɓaci cikin kwana biyu idan ba a yi amfani da shi ba, za a iya adana shi a cikin firijin na sama da wata guda ba tare da wani abu ya same shi ba matuƙar akwai wadataciyar wutar lantarki.

Hanya ta biyu da aka bi domin tattara bayanan wannan bincike ita ce hira. An tattauna da rukunin mutane daban-daban musamman mata da masu sana'ar abinci da kuma manoma. Hirarrakin sun mayar da hankali wajen samun bayanai game da:

- a. Bambancewa tsakanin abubuwan da suka kasance na gargajiya da na zamani dangane da abincin Hausawa,
- b. Ra'ayin Mutane game da sauye-sauyen zamani ga abincin Hausawa, da
- c. Ilimi ko rashin ilimi dangane da alfanu ko illoli da ke tattare da wasu abubuwan da zamani ya zo da su da suka shafi abincin Hausawa.

2.0 Ire-iren Tasirin Zamani a Kan Abincin Hausawa

Tasirin da zamani ya yi a kan abincin Hausawa bai kasance ta fuska daya kawai ba. A maimakon haka, tasirin ya samar da sauye-sauye ga wasu daga cikin abincin Hausawa ta fuskar yanayin shuka su da kuma yanayin sarrafa su. A daya bangaren kuma, akwai nau'o'in abincin bakin al'ummu da Bahausha ya kwaikwaya kuma ya mayar da su nasa ta hanyar yi musu kwaskwarima ko ma samar da su kamar yadda suke ga al'ummar da ya ara. A kasa an tattauna nau'ukan sauye-sauyen da abincin Hausawa na gargajiya ya samu a dalilin cudanyarsa da bakin al'ummu, da ma sababbin nau'ukan abinci da ya koya daga wadannan al'ummu.

2.1 Sauye-Sauye ga Abincin Gargajiya

Nau'o'in abincin Bahausha na gargajiya da dama sun fuskanci sauye-sauye a dalilin cudanyarsa da bakin al'ummu da kuma tasirin zamani a jimlace. Wannan ya shafi hanyoyin sarrafa abincin da kuma abubuwan da ake amfani da su yayin samar da abincin. Idan aka dauki bangaren noma misali, za a tarar da ire-iren wadannan sauye-sauye. Noma dai fitacciyar hanya ce mai tsohon tarihi ta samar da abinci ga Bahausha.³ A da, Bahausha yana amfani da hanyoyin noma ne na gargajiya domin samar da abincinsa. Wato yakan yi amfani da kayan noma kamar su garma/galma, da kalme, da gatari da lauje da sungumi da wuka da makamantansu. Sai ga shi zamani ya samar wa Bahausha kayan noma irin su tarakta (tantan) da habesta da ma wasu injimukka da suke taimakawa wajen gyaran gona, shuka iri, kula da shukar, ban ruwa, da ciran shukar makamantansu duk a cikin sauki.

A bangaren noma har ila yau, Bahausha ya wuce yin amfani da takin gargajiya kadai. A maimakon haka, yanzu yakan yi amfani da takin zamani da kuma wasu sinadarai ko magungunan kashe kwari da haki iri-iri. Wannan ma za a iya kallon sa a matsayin sauyi ga hanyoyin samar da abincin Bahausha wanda zamani ya zo da shi.

³Domin samun farin bayani game da matsayin noma ga rayuwar Bahausha sai a duba Bunza, (2014) da Shehu, (2015).

A ɓangare guda kuma, yadda ake sarrafa amfanin gona da na lambu da duk wani nau'in abincin da ake nomawa ya samu sauye-sauye a dalilin tasirin zamani. Wannan ya samo asali ne daga irin sinadaran da ake amfani da su da kuma su kansu hanyoyin sarrafawar. A yanzu wuraren adana abincin Bahaushe ba rumbu da ruhewa ne kawai ba. Yakan sanya maganin kwari ga amfanin gonan da ya girbe sannan ya adana cikin buhuna ko diro-diro ko jarkoki (ya danganta da nau'in amfanin), cikin sito-sito na adana amfanin gona.

A ɓangaren dafa abincin kansa akwai sauye-sauye. Misali, a can da, Bahaushe yana amfani da murhu kawai a matsayin abin dafa abinci a gida. Za mu iya tunawa da kacici-kacicin Bahaushe da ke cewa: "Uku-uku sun cika gari." Amma a yau, Bahaushe ya samu ci gaban amfani da wasu hanyoyin dafa abinci da suka maye gurbin murhun duwatsu da itace kadai (kamar yadda yake a da). Tuni ya fara amfani da kurho da gawayi da risho da elektirik kuka da gas kuka da makamantansu. Waɗannan kuwa duk zamani ne ya zo da su.

Haka ma a ɓangaren kayan haɗin abincin Bahaushe, tuni aka samu sababbin nau'o'in sinadarai daban-daban da suke da alaƙa da ƙarin kamshi ko dandano. Sun haɗa da magi da ajino moto da kori da dai sauransu.⁴ Jadawalin da ke ƙasa na dake da misalan sababbin al'amura da suka kasance a sha'anin abincin Bahaushe a yau:

Jadawalina 1: Sababbin Abubuwa a Harkar Samarwa da Sarrafa Abincin Bahaushe

Kayan Aikin Noma Na Zamani	Sinadaran Noma Na Zamani	Kayan Dafa Abinci Na Zamani	Sinadaran Abinci Na Zamani
Tarikita/tantan	Takin zamani	Risho	Magi

⁴A hirar da aka yi da Malama Zainab Sani (2021), ta bayyana cewa: "Ba sai an yi nisa sosai ba, ko shekaru hamsin baya aka duba za a tarar da cewa Hausawa ba su san mafi yawan kayan dandanon da suke amfani da su a girke-girkensu a yau ba."

Kayan Aikin Noma Na Zamani	Sinadaran Noma Na Zamani	KayanDafaAbinci Na Zamani	SinadaranAbinci Na Zamani
Janareta(injin ban-ruwa)	Maganinkwari	Kurho	Onga
Habesta	Maganinkasheciyawa	Gas kuka	Ajino moto
Injimin feshi	Maganin kara girman amfanin gona	Elektirikkuka	Kori
Injin sussuka/casa	Sinadarinajiyelema (damshi) a gona	Rayiskuka	Madish
Injimin shuka		Elektirikketil	Kirim salat
		Elektirik hita	Tumaturin gwangwani
		Bilenda	Koren wake
		Gireta	

Madogara: Hira da Sani, (2020) da Pawa, (2021) da Sulaiman, (2021) da Abubakar, (2021) da Usman, (2021)

1.2 Sababbin Abinci

Akwai nau'o'in abinci daban-daban da Bahaushe ya samu sakamakon cudanyarsa da bakin al'ummu. Saboda haka, za a iya kallon ire-iren wadannan abinci a matsayin

abincin zamani ga Bahaushe. Nau’o’in abincin sun bambanta ta fuskar dandanonu da kayan hadinsu da kuma siffofinsu da waɗanda Bahaushe ya saba amfani da su kafin cudanyarsa da bakin al’ummu. Don haka, za a iya kasafta nau’o’in sababbin abincin Bahaushe zuwa rukunai uku; wato abincin bukukuwa da na yau-da-kullum da kuma na kwalama.

2.2.1 Sababbin Abinci na Bukukuwa

Cudanyar Bahaushe da bakin al’ummu ya sanya nason al’adun waɗannan al’ummu a cikin al’adun Bahaushe. Daga ciki har da al’adun da suka shafi bukukuwa kamar na aure da haihuwa da makamantansu. Wannan kuwa ya yi taliyon da ya shafi nau’o’in abincin da ake samarwa a lokacin waɗannan bukukuwa. Sababbin abincin bukukuwan da Bahaushe ya samu sun haɗa da:

1. Dabila
2. Fish-fayit (fish-pie)
3. Fof-fof/cincin
4. Kek
5. Mit-fayit (meat-pie)

2.2.2 Sababbin Abinci Na Yau-da-Kullum

Bayan abincin bukukuwa, zamani ya kawo wa Bahaushe wasu sababbin nau’o’in abincin da ake ci yau-da-kullum. Ire-iren waɗannan abinci sun haɗa da:

1. Firayid rayis
2. Garin tuwon samo
3. Indomi
4. Kuskus
5. Makaroni
6. Taliyar kanti

2.2.3 Sababbin Abincin Makulashe

A ɓangaren kƙalama ma, zamani ya kawo sauyi. Akwai nau'oin abinci daban-daban da zamani ya kawo, waɗanda kuma suna wannan rukuni na abincin kƙalama.

Misalansu sun haɗa da:

1. Gullisuwa
2. Kek
3. Liyafa
4. Tawaita/tayota
5. Tuwon madara

2.2.4 Sababbin Ababen Sha

A ɓangaren ababen sha ma, zamani ya yi tasiri wajen samar da wasu sababbin abubuwan sha da Bahaushe ba shi da su a da. Wasu daga cikin waɗannan sababbin ababen sha da zamani ya kawo su ne:

1. Jinja
2. Kunun dankali/kudaku
3. Kunun shinkafa
4. Kwastad
5. Tafiyota/kafiyota
6. Jus na kwakwa
7. Zobo/sobo
8. Furutt salat
9. Fosta kilak
10. Bebi mis
11. Tiyara
12. Kunun gyada
13. Kunun aya

2.3 Dalilan Tasirin Abincin Zamani a Kan na Hausawa

Za a iya hasashen dalilan da suka karfafa wannan tasiri na abincin zamani a kan na gargajiyar Bahaushe kamar haka:

1. Nau'o'in abincin zamani sun zo da mabambanta dandano da kamshi idan aka kwatanta su da nau'o'in abincin Bahaushe na gargajiya. Hakan na faruwa ne a dalilin nau'o'in kayan kamshi daban-daban da kuma sauran kayan hadin abinci da ake amfani da su yayin girka abincin na zamani.
2. Haka kuma, ire-iren abincin na zamani sun fito da wata kafa ta sabunta nau'o'in abincin Bahaushe na gargajiya da ya dade da su, kuma ya gaji da su (suka gundure shi). Kamar yadda Koester & Mojet, (2007: 100) suka nuna, a fahimtar Ra'in Kayamar Abinci da Neman Nau'i, mutane sukan so samun sauyi a nau'ukan abincin da suka riga da suka gundure su.
3. Ire-iren abincin zamani sun zo da wani sabon salo na musamman mai kayatarwa ta fuskar tsaftarsu da fasalin jikinsu. Misali, garin tuwon samo yana zuwa ne a tsabtace cikin leda. Wannan ya kasance koma bayan garin gero ko na masara ko na dawa wanda sai an gyara an nika an tankade kafin amfani da shi.
4. Nau'o'in abincin na zamani da yawansu suna da sauƙin dafawa. Ma'ana akan dafa abincin cikin kankanin lokaci ba tare da an sha dogon aiki ba. Misalan nau'ukan abincin zamani da ke dahuwa da wuri sun hada da kuskus da indomi.

Hakika, waɗannan dalilai sun taka muhimmiyar rawa wajen kawo tasirin abincin zamani kan na gargajiyar Bahaushe. A yanzu, ya tabbata cewa, hatta abincin Bahaushe na gargajiya (misali kunun koko da kunun tsamiya da tuwon dawa da makamantansu) akan bi hanyoyin zamani yayin dafa su. Wannan na faruwa ta hanyar sanya musu wasu kayan haɗi na zamani, wato dangin kayan kamshi da kuma kayan yaji.

2.4 Sakamakon Tasirin Zamani a Kan Abincin Hausawa

Tabbas, zamani ya yi tasiri a kan sha'anin abincin Hausawa ya haifar da wasu sauye-sauye ga abincin na Hausawa. Mafi yawa daga cikin wadannan sauye-sauye ana kallonsu da mizanin ci gaba ga al'ada. Ko da yake, ba za a rasa 'yan kalilan da suka kasance koma baya ga rayuwar Bahausha ba, musamman ta fuskar sanya lalaci da kasala da sakalci yayin da aka samu hanya mafi sauki na gudanar da lamura. Za a kuma iya hasashen raguwar ingancin wasu daga cikin kayan amfanin gona da Bahausha ya saba samarwa a baya. A takaice, an kawo wasu daga cikin ci gaba da zamani ya samar ga sha'anin abincin Bahausha. An kasafta wannan ci gaba zuwa fannin amfanin gona, da kuma bangaren dafa-dafen abinci.

2.4.1 Ci Gaban da Zamani ya Samar wa Noman Bahausha

- i. Injin ban-ruwa na zamani, wato janareta yana taimakawa kwarai wajen noman rani mai yawa ta hanyar saukafa bayi ga amfanin da ake nomawa.⁵
- ii. Samuwar magungunan kwari na feshin amfanin gona sun kawo raguwar dambin hasarorin amfanin gona da ake samu a dalilin barnar kwari a gonaki. Aktar, Sengupta, & Chowdhury, (2009: 1-2) sun zayyano wasu daga cikin alfanun amfani da magungunan feshi a gona. Sun hada da (a) haɓaka amfanin gona da (b) kare amfani daga kwari da (c) kare amfanin gona daga cututtuka.
- iii. Takin zamani ya zo da bayyanannen sauyi ga haɓaka da girman amfanin gona cikin gaggawa. Roberts, (2009: 15) ya bayyana cewa, ta hanyar amfani da takin zamani ne kadai amfanin gona da ake samarwa zai iya wadatar dambin al'ummar da ke rayuwa a duniya.
- iv. Zamani ya zo da injunan noma da ke saukafa aiki. Amfani da ire-iren wadannan injuna na bayar da damar yin aiki mai tarin yawa cikin kankanan lokaci sannan cikin sauki. Daga cikin injunan noma da suka iso kasar Hausa a yau akwai tarikita/tantan da injin sussuka. Magdoff, (2016) ya gudanar da

⁵Domin samun farin bayani ana iya duba ayyukan Mohamed, (2012) da Scherer, (2017).

- bincike game da amfani da injunan zamani domin inganta harkar noma. A shafi na 33, ya nuna cewa, duk da cewa yawan amfani da ake samu ya dogora kan abubuwa da dama kamar takin zamani da kyan kasa da sauransu, to injunan noma na zamani ma na taka muhimmiyar rawa a wannan fanni.
- v. Zamani ya zo da nau'oin irin shuka da ke da saurin nuna. Sukan taimaka a samu amfanin gona kafin ruwan damina ya dauke ko da a shekarar an samu karancin ruwan sama. Wasu daga cikinsu kuma na ba wa manoma damar shuka sau biyu a damina guda a maimakon sau daya. Oyekale, (2014: 345) ya bayyana cewa, amfani da irin shuka mai inganci na daya daga cikin abin da ke taimaka wa samar da abinci a Nijeriya.

2.4.2 Nakasu/Kalubalen Kayan Noman Zamani

- i. Amfani da maganin feshin kwari na da bukatar kwarewa. Bayan haka, magungunan suna dauke da illoli daban-daban. Aktar, Sengupta, & Chowdhury, (2009: 2-8) sun kawo wasu daga cikin illolin magungunan feshi da suka hada da (a) illa ga lafiyar dan adam kai tsaye ko ta cikin abinci da (b) gurbata kasa da (c) gurbata ruwan rafuka da tekunan da ke kusa (d) kashe kwarin cikin kasa da sauransu. Wilson, & Tisdell, (2001: 449-462) sun jaddada wadannan illoli.
- ii. Tamkar dai magungunan feshi, shi ma takin zamani na da matuƙar illa ga lafiyar dan adam da sauran halittu na cikin kasa da na ruwa. Chandini, Kumar, Kumar, & Prakash, (2019) sun gudanar da bincike dangane da illolin takin zamani. Tsakanin shafi na 76 zuwa 80 sun bayyana matsalolin amfani da takin zamani da suka hada da (i) gurbata ruwa da (ii) gurbata iskar shaka da (iii) kashe halittun cikin kasa da (iv) sanya wa amfani sinadarai masu illa ga lafiyar dan adam da sauransu. Baya ga wannan, wasu kalubalen da ke tattare da takin zamani a kasar Hausa sun hada da (a) karancin ilimin amfani da

- takin zamanin da kuma (b) tsadar takin zamanin wanda ke sanya manoma Hausawa da dama ba sa iya mallakar sa.
- iii. Injunan noma na da tsada, sannan akwai buƙatar ƙwarewa kafin a iya amfani da su. Saboda haka, ba su kasance masu sauƙi ba ga talakawa, waɗanda kuma su ne kaso mafi tsoka na manoman Hausawa. Ko bayan wannan, Magdoff, (2016: 42) ya kawo wasu kalubalen da ke tattare da amfani da injunan noma na zamani. Sun haɗa da rage ingancin amfanin gona da halin ko-in-kula da gwamnatoƙi ke yi game da ingancin injunan yayin shigo da su daga ƙasashen ƙetare. Bayan wannan kuma, samuwar injunan noma na zamani ya janyo rashin aikin yi ga matasa da talakawa da dama. Wannan ya samu ne kasancewar injin noma ɗaya zai iya yin aikin da sai matasa da dama sun taru kafin su iya gudanarwa.
 - iv. Jahilci na hana manoma Hausawa musamman waɗanda ke karkara amfani da irin amfani gona na zamani. Kafin su karɓi wannan sauyi, akan sha wahala ƙwarai wajen wayar musu da kai tare da yi musu gwajin gani-da-ido. Bayan haka Oyekale, (2014: 352-353) ya kawo wasu kalubale da ke tattare da shirin amfani da iri na zamani. Sun haɗa da (a) samar da irin zamani da ingancinsu bai kai yadda ake so ba da (b) rashin mayar da hankali kan shirin samar da irin zamani da (c) rashin ingancin hanyoyi da matakan rarraba iri zuwa ga manoma da (d) rashin isasshen horaswa da isar da bayanai ga manoma.

A ɗaya ɓangaren kuma, zamani ya kawo sauye-sauye ga sha'anin dafa abincin Bahaushe. Wannan ma hanjin jimina ne, akwai na ci akwai na zubarwa. A ƙasa an kawo alfanu da nakasun zamani ga sha'anin dafa abincin Bahaushe a takaice:

2.4.3 Ci Gaban da Zamani ya Samar ga Dafa Abincin Bahaushe

- i. Zamani ya samar da kayayyakin dafa abinci da suka wakilci itace da murhu. Daga cikin waɗannan kayayyaki akwai risho da gas kuka da elektirik kuka da makamantansu. Irin waɗannan kayan girki sun fi itace da murhu sauri, sannan

ba sa bakanta tukunya (in ban da risho). Wani ci gaba da suka samar shi ne na rage saran dazuka (domin neman itacen girki). Bayan haka, kauce wa amfani da itace da murhu na rage adadin hayaki da ke tashi zuwa sararin samani (wanda yake da illa ga yanayi). Stabridis & Gameren, (2018: 9) ya rawaito maganar WHO, (2006) da ke jaddada illar amfani da itace a matsayin hanyar girki. Itatuwan na fitar da sinadarin *kabon monozayid* wanda ke da illa yayin da aka shaƙe shi.

- ii. Zamani ya kawo farin kayan hadin abinci, dangin kayan kamshi da farin dandano (kamar yadda aka kawo misali cikin jadawali na 1 da ke sama).
- iii. Zamani ya zo da nau'ukan abinci da suke iya dahuwa cikin gaggawa (fast foods). Daga cikinsu akwai indomi da kuskus da makamantansu. Dafa ire-iren waɗannan nau'ukan abinci ba ya ɗaukar lokaci. A takaice ke nan, za a samu biyan bukata cikin kankanan lokaci.
- iv. Zamani ya zo da nau'ukan abincin da ke iya ɗaukar tsawon lokaci ba tare da sun lalace ba. Daga cikinsu akwai cincin da kek da dibila da sauran makamantansu.
- v. Samuwar firijin ya ba da damar ajiye wasu nau'ukan abinci na tsawon lokaci ba tare da sun lalace ba. A yau ana iya ajiye nau'ukan abinci a cikin firijin irin su kayan marmari da na maƙulashe, har ma da tuwo da miya.

2.4.4 Nakasun Tasirin Zamani Kan Abincin Bahausha

- i. Gidajen Hausawa masu karamin karfi ba sa iya amfani da kayayyakin girki na zamani. Wannan na faruwa ko dai a dalilin tsadar kayayyakin ko kuma saboda karancin ilimi game da su da kuma yadda ake amfani da su.
- ii. Kayayyakin girki na zamani irin su gas kuka da elektirik kuwa suna da matuƙar hatsari, musamman idan aka yi amfani da su ta hanyoyin da suka kauce wa ka'ida.⁶

⁶Bincike game da hanyoyin inganta amfani da waɗannan kayayyaki na da matuƙar muhimmanci. A kafar intanet ta YouTube, akwai laccoci da dama game da yadda ake amfani da kayayyakin girki na zamani (cikin bidiyoyi).

- iii. Sinadaran dafa abinci na zamani da ke kara kamshi da dandano suna da illa ga lafiyar dan adam, musamman idan suka yi yawa ko aka yi amfani da su ba ta hanyoyin da suka dace ba. Srinivasan, (2016) ya gudanar da bincike game da kayan girki na farin dandano da kamshi. Ya bayyana nau'ukan amfani da suke da shi. A shafi na 103 ya bayyana cewa, amfani da su na iya cutar da fatar cikin ciki da ake kira *gastric mucosa*.
- iv. Yawancin nau'ukan abincin da ke dahuwa da wuri (fast foods) suna da illa ga lafiyar dan adam. Dangane da yawan cin nau'ukan abinci masu dahuwa da wuri, Mohiuddin, (2020: 8) na cewa:

The growing widespread use of fast food among adolescents and young adults is of concern due to the high fat and energy intake, which may cause obesity and subsequently obesity-related chronic diseases.

Fassara

Karuwar yawaitar amfani da nau'ukan abinci masu dahuwa da wuri da matasa⁷ ke yi abu ne mai damarwa la'akari da yawan adadin maiko da sauran sinadaren da ke cikinsu. Wadannan sinadarai na iya haifar da kiba ta rashin lafiya tare da wasu cututtuka masu tsanani da ke da dangantaka da kiba.

Major Md Serazul Islam, psc (2020) sun gudanar da gagarumin bincike kan illolin amfani da nau'ukan abinci masu dahuwa da wuri. A shafi na 22, sun zayyano wasu illolin amfani da ire-iren wadannan abinci. Daga cikin illolin akwai ciwon sukari da kiba na rashin lafiya da hawan jini da makamantansu. Wani & Sarode, (2018: 82) sun kawo jadawali da ke nuna mutane da dama na kamuwa da cututtuka sakamakon amfani da nau'ukan abinci masu saurin dahuwa bisa jahiltar illolin wadannan nau'ukan abinci.

⁷Maganar Mohiuddin, (2020) na nuna cewa matasa ne suka fi amfani da nau'ukan abinci masu dahuwa da wuri. Wannan ya yi daidai da tunanin ra'in Kyamar Abinci da Neman Nau'i, wato kamar yadda Tuorila et al., (2001) ya nuna cewa tsofi su ne suka fi guje wa sababbin nau'ukan abinci.

- v. Mafi yawan nau'ukan abincin zamani da ke dafewa ba tare da sun faci ba kayan makulashe ne wadanda ke dauke da mai ko sukari da yawa. Ire-irensu kuwa na da illa ga lafiyar dan adam. Mohiuddin, (2020: 8) ya tabbatar da samuwar ire-iren wadannan sinadarai a cikin nau'ukan abincin inda yake cewa: "The added fat, sugar, and salt create a taste that makes people crave these foods." Wato maiko da dandanon (da ake samu cikin wadannan nau'ukan abinci) shi ke sa mutane suna kara kwadaituwa da su. Kaur, (2017: 492) ya tabbatar da cewa nau'ukan abincin makulashe masu maiko ko sikari na janyo kiba na rashin lafiya da ciwon sukari. Ashkirani & Deepthi, (2012: 10) sun bayyana cewa nau'ukan makulashe da ake soyawa suna dauke da maiko da sinadaren kolasteral wadanda ke da illa ga zuciya da koda.

3.0 Sakamakon Bincike da Shawarwari

Lallai an samu sauye-sauye masu dumbin yawa dangane da cimakar Bahausha. Wannan ya fara tun daga hanyoyin samar da abincin (noma) har zuwa yadda ake sarrafa su (dafawa). A harkar noma an samu sauye-sauye tun daga bangaren kayan noma na zamani (misali tarikita da habesta da injin shuka da sauransu), har zuwa maganin feshi da na kashe ciyawa da kuma amfani da irin zamani mai jure wa fari da tare da saurin nuna. A bangaren dafa abinci kuwa, akwai kayayyakin girke-girke da aka samu a zamanance (kamar risho da gas kuka da rayis kuka). A bangare guda kuwa, an kwaikwayi abincin bakin al'ummu inda aka yi wa wasu daga cikinsu kwaskwarima. Duka wadannan sauye-sauye ba su zo da mamaki ba bisa ra'ayin Ra'in Kyamar Abinci da Neman Nau'i. Dalili kuwa shi ne, da ma ra'in ya tabbatar da dan adam a kullum na neman sauyi game da cimakarsa domin sabuntawa daga abincin da ya gundure shi.

Ansamu ci gabasosaisakamakonabubuwan da zamaniya zo da su da sukadangancisamarwa da sarrafaabincinBahausha. Injunannoma da magungunanfeshi da nau'ukanirinazamaniduksamar da sauki da ci gaba ga al'amuran noman Bahausha a yau. A bangarn dafa abinci kuwa, amfani da kayan dafa abinci na zamani irin su gas

kuka ya taimaka wajen rage saran daji (wanda ke janyo gurgusowar hamada da fari), sannan ya taimaka wajen rage gurbatar iska sakamakon sinadarin da ke cikin hayakin da itatuwa ke fitarwa. Bugu da fari, samuwar sababbin nau'ukan abinci da kayan dandano da na kamshi ci gaba ne.⁸

A daya bangaren kuma, duk da dūnbin amfanin abubuwan da zamani ya zo da su da suka shafi samar da abinci da sarrafa shi, akwai illoli da dama tattare da su. An ga ire-iren kalubalen da ke tattare da harkar noman zamani a maganganun Oyekale, (2014: 352-353) da Magdoff, (2016: 42). Haka su kansu kayayyakin girki na zamani na da nasu matsaloli kamar yadda suka zo a maganganun Ashkirani & Deepthi, (2012: 10) da Srinivasan, (2016: 103) da Wani & Sarode, (2018: 82) da Mohiuddin, (2020: 8).

Lura da duka wadannan, wannan takarda na ba da shawarwari kamar haka:

- i. Gwamnati ta zage damtse wajen samar da kyawawan shirye-shirye da za su ba wa manoma horaswa da wayewan kai game da amfani da dabaru da kayayyakin noma na zamani. Wannan yunkuri ya kasance tare da haɗin guiwar malaman jami'o'i da gidajen talabijin da na rediyo tare da kafafen intanet.
- ii. Gwamnati ta kara kaimi wajen samar da shirye-shiryen tallafa wa manoma da kayan noman zamani da suka shafi kayan aiki da iri da magungunan feshi. A tabbatar da inganci da nasarar shirin ta hanyar bibiyar inda aka kwana a-kai-a-kai.
- iii. A samu huɓɓasa ta haɗaka tsakanin gwamnati da masana da gidajen talabijin da na rediyo da jaridu da kafafen intanet wajen wayar da kai da ilimantar da al'umma dangane da amfani da kayayyakin girki na zamani. Wannan ya shafi nuna wa al'umma matakan da ya dace su dāuka domin kaucewa illoli da ke tattare da kayayyakin.

⁸Za a iya samun karin bayani game da muhimmancin abubuwan da zamani ya zo da su da suka shafi noma da girki cikin ayyukan WHO, (2006) da Roberts, (2009) da Aktar, Sengupta, & Chowdhury, (2009) da Oyekale, (2014) da Magdoff, (2016) da Stabridis & Gamera, (2018).

- iv. Mafi yawancin takardu da littattafai da masana kiyon lafiya ke rubutawa dangane da abinci da noma sun kasance cikin wasu harsuna na daban ba Hausa ba. A samu wani kokari daga masana harshen Hausa na fassara ire-iren waɗànnan rubuce-rubuce zuwa harshen Hausa (wanda hakan zai kasance tare da izinin masu asalin aikin).

4.0 Kammalawa

Hakika, kamar yadda zamani ya yi tasiri a bangarorin rayuwar Bahaushe daban-daban, wannan tasiri ya shafi hanyoyin samarwa da sarrafa abincin Bahaushe. Sai dai sauye-sauyen da aka samu sun kasance hanjin jimina, wato akwai na ci akwai na zubarwa. Duk da haka, za a amfana da wannan ci gaba na zamani sosai yayin da aka bi matakan da suka dace. Wannan ya shafi kokarin gwamnatoji da masana da sauran rukunonin al'umma a mataakai daban-daban domin wayar da kai da ilimantarwa tare da daukar mataakai da suka kamata don ganin an ci gajiyar abubuwan da ci gaban zamani ke zuwa da su, tare da kauce wa illolinsu.

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